

THE ROLE OF SOCIETY TRANSLATORSHIP IN CROSS-CULTURAL INTERACTIONⁱ

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Abstract:

Globalization and mass migration cause living of different cultures together. Immigrants take their own culture to foreign countries. Hence, cultural varieties occur in target countries. Foreign cultures cannot be reshaped, so different cultures meet and live together in target countries. Integration of different cultures is an obligation for cultural pluralism. In order to build a multicultural and tolerant society, society translators who know the cultures of immigrant societies have some important roles. In addition, society translators could contribute to building a stable integration in target countries. Hence, it is important to train society translators not only on target language, but also on target culture. This study has qualitative design investigates contemporary cross-cultural interaction, cultural variety, hybrid cultures and multi-culturalism by interpreting the obtained data. In addition to these, contribution of society translators who know the cultures of immigrant societies to building multicultural policies will also be investigated.

Keywords: culture, cultural integration, society translator

1. Introduction

In today's world, many different cultures can come together because of globalization, media and migration. Thus, it is formed a cultural and social diversity of the different cultures that live together. Some exchanges or borrowing can be concerned as a result of

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cultural interactions. Cultural hybridization can be said in this place. The reason is that cultures cannot be reproduced. External factors considered, it can undergo change in social ties in the living environment. The communities who live together with different cultures expect 'to understand the differences' and 'to be understood' in their daily lives by minimizing the differences. This process is the resolution phase and these kinds of approaches help different cultures come together. A social structure, the base of multicultural society life is a product of this approach. Multiculturalism as a political organization is living of the communities with different cultures, and to benefit from all public services without losing their own differences and without being marginalized. Multiculturalism as a wealth of social and cultural context finds a chance to live with intercultural interaction.

The encounter of societies that exhibit different cultural values and behaviors also brings conflict in the process of intercultural interaction. It is possible to emerge conflicts between the societies from different cultures who live together. The differences in perceptions and interpretations will affect negatively multicultural nature. At this point, "Community Interpreters" as social compromisers who know both cultures well should be employed.

"Community Interpreting" is a way of oral translation which granting of services for societies with different cultures. However, in order to ensure the harmonization of different cultures seen as a structure, "Community Interpreting" is seen necessary. The implementation of the adjustment program will be prepared in accordance with the expectations of the task is carried out by Community Interpreters.

As a result of cross-cultural communication, multicultural societies will continue to exist by eliminating the need around shared values. Interruption of relations with each of the communities will lead to polarization in society and at the same time, cutting the interaction of cultures. Evaluation by analyzing the different cultures that live together will benefit to form education around common values. To take part in such embodiments of "Community Interpreters" is important to recognize cultural differences.

It is inevitable for intercultural dialogues in order to solve the problems which arise in the common living area. For this reason, it is possible to raise people, who are effective, understanding differences, have a say in international fields by education programs within cultural diversities. In this context, multiculturalism will grow stronger without marginalizing the cultural differences and by taking multiculturalism as mainstay.

2. The Definition of Culture

Every society has its own culture. Culture determines the life of the community in which there is. Individuals shape their personalities, way of thinking, cultural values in a particular community. In certain periods, even though “culture” used equally with “civilization” in some languages, culture is much more mental and spiritual values. In this sense, culture means except natural events, but in historical periods, using every value produced by society. Briefly, culture is everything that comes from “human-hand and tongue.” The concept of culture involves different meanings over time. According to Yanık, culture is;

The concept of culture can show changes according to writer’s view or sociological theories. However, the word of “culture” is derived from Latin word ‘colere’ which means sustainable, and again is derived from ‘cultura’ and this word means “taming the earth, plowing fields, cultivating”.

(Yanık, 2013:23)

Culture is a dynamic phenomenon. Because, it needs a particular accumulation in the life processes of societies. Culture has its own rules and community life it is ongoing in this regard. In this sense, Güvenç defines culture as;

A society’s way of doing business, framing this business with rules, and becoming a series of social processes. Culture is learnable, history and continuous. Culture is a social phenomenon and a system of idealized rules. Above all, culture changes. Elements of culture tend to form a system that is compatible and integrated as a product of adaptation period.

(www.ataaof.edu.tr/wp-content/uploads/KulturlerarasiIletisim.pdf)

The concept of culture has a plenty of definition which has close meanings. Below there are some dictionary definitions of culture:

The overall material and spiritual values transferred from generation to generation, faith, idea, science, art, customs and traditions, life and behavior styles

(M.E.B., 1999:1826)

Culture constitutes a society’s perception of thinking, lives, and thoughts as cultural values, all of language and art forms, and extensive and systematic knowledge.

(<http://frmsinsi.net/showread.php?t=958968>)

Culture is all historical and social development processes, using these values in transferring from generation to generation, and also showing sovereignty of people.

<http://frmsinsi.net/showhread.php?t=958968>

Language has the key role in transferring culture from generation to generation in a society. Language as a transfer agent reserves cultural continuity and enables it to be permanent. Transfer of culture can be both written and oral. Written culture is depended on particular texts with one author, but with different readers. Oral culture is depended on memorization which is anonymous, natural and without any author. In this sense, oral culture is variable, and can be diversified locally.

Every society is evaluated within its own cultures. Cultures diversities and wealth are pretty much. In this context, the most important thing is recognition of different cultures and being able to negotiate with them. And this is possible with translation.

3. Cultural Interaction and Multiculturalism

People are always in touch with other nations in different places during the history. And this enabled interaction between different cultures. In these connections among different nations, their culture is affected or it affected other cultures. Today, the rapid development in technology, international mobility of the people in the area of transportation, the exceeding properties and capitals enabled different cultures come together. Media, and also developments in the information technology made international relations compulsory. Moreover, migrations for various reasons caused different cultures come together. Depending on the result of this encounter of different cultures, societies and individuals, interaction between cultures brings with it. In this sense, Tomilson says (2004):

The rapidly growing social-institutional relations among individuals and communities, worldwide commodities across national boundaries, increased flow of people and practical knowledge, establishing more concrete ties like international air transport and electronic communication systems also contribute to multiculturalism.

<http://www.ataaof.edu.tr/wp-content/uploads/Kulturlerarasilletiřim.pdf>

By uniting of different cultures, the occurrence of cultural interaction, understanding of one other's thoughts, values, and attitudes are possible. Cultural differences leading misunderstandings may be solved within dialogues. Destruction of

cultural prejudices is depended on the knowing and understanding the differences. Moreover, a person who knows his culture well does not find difficult to understand and evaluate the different culture. In this sense, the differences are effective in evaluating one's own cultural values. Intercultural interaction also contributes recognition of communities in all aspects. It is possible to save from time and property with the help of other nations' experiences and accumulations. Moreover, it affects positively to create universal cultural values. Thus, intercultural interaction helps permanent world peace. Keeping different cultures together and enabling positive intercultural interaction are possible with multicultural education.

Moving from the idea that keeping different nations together and being keep in touch with each other, upbringing competent individuals in international fields is possible with multicultural nations. In this sense, without marginalizing the other, seeing no reason to be in conflict, seeing differences as property, multicultural nations should be created. Multiculturalism is a way of political organization. According to Parekh (2002) multiculturalism is:

The concept of culture is a way of assessing and evaluating cultural issues. Moreover, it a diversity that comes from organized communities and cultural communities.

(www.dergiler.ankara.edu.tr)

Multiculturalism gives opportunity not only intercultural communication but also cultural privilege to the communities. In the frame of multiculturalism, religious practices, language and forms of special education is formed. According to Doytcheva, multiculturalism:

A whole experience based on a historical political program, intellectual discussion, and practical knowledge. It reforms the institutions of modern democracies, giving opportunities to individuals their different aspects and enabling cultural transformation.

(Doytcheva, 2009:25)

Attributing to multicultural diversity and the development of individuals will help to ease every world problems.

Multicultural lifestyle and intercultural interaction brings some difficulties with itself. As a person tries to accommodate to the other culture, the change in his own cultural values is pretty difficult. In this sense, culture shock can be experienced. Forcing to cultural changes can cause cultural degeneration. Misunderstanding cultural differences and making wrong analysis about culture cause social conflicts. In this

sense, Community Interpreters have a key role in acquiring governmental integrity and permanency. Community Interpreters, not only knowing the language, but also knowing the culture, helps to obtain other nations.

4. The Definition of Community Interpreters

Translation is a tool to overcome obstacles in written or oral communication when different languages are used. In recent years, Community Interpreting gains importance as providing the need of communication as well as ensuring continuity. Below there are some dictionary meanings of Community Interpreters:

In English, “public service interpreting”, in French interpretariat communautaire, in German, Sprach-und Kulturmittler, Sprach-Intergrationsmittler or Gemeindedolmetscher, in Austria Kommunaldolmetscher, and in Swiss Interkultureller Übersetzer.

([www.sprint-wuppertal.de/index.php/...](http://www.sprint-wuppertal.de/index.php/)).

In historical period, social aspects of translation as a tool for communication between individuals are not on the agenda. But translation is a social phenomenon and has a big role in intercultural communication. Translation should be evaluated not only in the context of text-translator but also within the cultural system. Translation is much more than transferring the text to the reader. It should answer the expectations of output and target nations. Moving from this idea, community interpreting is used for different cultural expectations.

In today, it is known that multicultural nations (like Canada, France, Swiss) create programs in order to introduce different nations and cultures, reforming the institutions for being social and peaceful state. This program includes cultural values, relief measures, language and special education. It is important to be told the differences and creating dialogues. Community Interpreters will help to make multiculturalism permanent. In briefly, Community Interpreters have the key role in this program.

Moving from the study of E. A. Nida, translation is not only language but also cultural and social processes; Community Interpreters are the representatives of their own nations and also have a social role as knowing the other nations' cultures. This thought shows Community Interpreting is an important institution that helps to maintain public order and harmony of other societies. There is an important relation between Community Interpreting and social status. And this is only possible with

competent people who took translation education. Especially for the countries like Turkey which is transition areas for migration, proficiency training for Community Interpreters is so important. In this sense, Kurultay thinks:

In historical processes most affected country from migration, Turkey, in terms of its geopolitical location, some arrangements should be done in education and access to the governmental services, and also in the functions of social systems.

(Kurultay, 2012, s.84)

Community Interpreters have great responsibilities in cultural properties, permanency of social diversity that forming societies from different nations.

5. The Role of Community Interpreters in Intercultural Communication

Cultural globalization and the convergence of the interaction with the media and migration for various reasons play a large role. Cultures change during the process of communication. Different cultural values of the society are emerging. These are societies with different cultural values is a result of creating a common life. Cultural communication enables societies to understand themselves. If this process happens unconsciously, it can damage social structures of societies. And this means losing one's own values and becoming degenerated. Cultural conflicts may occur when people's own cultural values, attitudes and behaviors are not appropriate. Any force can create conflict in the process of cultural communication. Cultural interaction requires respect to the different nations and approaching with tolerance. The person or society that cannot fit this can live culture shock. Cultural interaction in the formation of a multicultural society can have many negative aspects in addition to the positive ones. In order to overcome all these problems, there is a need to mediating role between cultures within the community interpreter.

According to Wolf (2006); Cultural interpreter during his action and thought to have contributed to the community affected, the removal of the distance between differences and means to achieve the universal cultural values. Cultural interaction process, without any obligation and condition of all cultural differences and find the opportunity to express themselves will be realized with the help of community interpreters in social life. Because, the most effective institution for incorporation of a multicultural society is Community Interpreting. Good communication among cultures will accelerate the integration process. Ensuring dialogues in societies in a cultural aspect can be outfitted with Community Interpreters.

According to A.Pym (2006); translation has become a sociological transformation. What is to say that neither a language nor a translator or a text can be a process? From all these, it is said that the results of translation are a phenomenon which affects and transforms all people in a society. For this reason, Community Interpreters should consider the principles below in their studies;

1. Loyalty;
2. Privacy;
3. Impartiality;
4. Respect for Individual Rights;
5. The Protection of Duty Limits.

These principles should be considered by Community Interpreters. Lack of insecurity during the service of the community will prevent harmonization. Intercultural communication is the responsibility of the Community Interpreters, on the other hand are obliged to practitioners of the government's multicultural policy. Diversity resulted from cultural interaction should be appropriate with the common lifestyle. Great responsibility falls on the community interpreters in terms of the survival of the cultural richness. Doytcheva explains his thought as follows:

Cultural diversity policies must satisfy social needs. Otherwise, multicultural program will deprived from social support. It may be even a threat to modern country like Canada. (as in Quebec region).

(Doytcheva 2005:39)

At this point, multiculturalism was intended to endure the transformation of society. Community Interpreters have a duty to make individuals active participants to the society. Habermas (1990) on the democratic rights of people belonging to different cultures, communication and social experience of participating in the study stressed the importance of the role of the interpreter community activities are supported by the state.

6. Conclusion

It is not possible to remain unaffected from different cultures. In today, there are various reasons for coexistence of different cultures. Especially with the requirements of the modern age of communication and information technology, society is inevitably put into a relationship with a different society and aims to promote cultural products. One of the reasons other encounter of different cultures and that is the most effective

international migration. The migration made at an international level for various reasons, plays a major role in the formation of a multicultural society. Another reason to be in a meeting and interaction of cultures in the world are changes in economic and political fields. In short, it is globalization. Mobility in the field of transportation brought about by globalization is to ensure that in the encounter and interaction of different cultures. In societies characterized by intense cultural relations, it is also seen as the exchange of cultural products and differentiation. In the framework of common values, nations with different cultures can create their own cultural values.

Communities that live together have a chance to live their own culture also supports cultural diversity. The formation of a multicultural social order that reflects the unity of the cultural richness of intercultural interaction that takes place with the positive direction. Experiencing cultural freedom, seen as a political system in which the public service is equal multiculturalism, life values, makes it necessary to approach with tolerance for differences. Some negative effects can arise because of cultural differences. Translation as a social phenomenon to make multiculturalism possible has a vital role in intercultural communication.

Multiculturalism is a social contract which meeting different cultures. Moving from this idea, this contract should include Community Interpreters who knows other cultures best. Community Interpreters are experts with equipment to support different cultural interactions. Community Interpreters should be supported for the reasons that it maintains nations in peace and maintaining permanency.

The understanding of modern state has brought the life chance to different cultures. Community Interpreters should obey these principles for national and social responsibilities. These are important for the people or communities' rights and freedoms. The most accurate way to serve the community and individuals in need of an interpreter or intercultural communication is necessary to satisfy the masses in terms of ensuring effective manner.

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